

The role of older people in society has evolved over time. Just as in more traditional cultures, the elderly are still a respected and revered figure, modern societies have relegated the role of older people in today's society to the background. Inclusion, participation and the recovery of their space is essential to offer a more optimistic perspective of what the elderly represent.

Below, [Faivish Pewzner](#), the COO of The Americare Companies, talks more about the role of senior in today's society.

From respect to oblivion: evolution of the role of the elderly in society

Experience is an important source of knowledge and wisdom. Since ancient times, older people have held a key position in society. They were asked for advice when it came to solving problems, no one knew the environment better than them and how to obtain resources and also time had endowed them with countless stories that everyone wanted to know.

Just three centuries ago, the percentage of people reaching old age was very limited. The further we go back in time, the more extraordinary was the presence of individuals over 60 years of age. This also explains why the older adult was a respected figure who had to be cared for and cared for. The future of many people depended on his wise decisions.

With the irruption of technology and the expansion of knowledge, the teachings of the elderly ceased to occupy that privileged place. Little by little, it was not only their stories and lessons that fell into oblivion: so did the interest in striving to care for people who, from a practical point of view, no longer provided a contribution of strength, protection or wealth to the society.

Thus, older adults went from becoming an added value to being a burden to the community. A reductionist and biased view of a population group that, both then and now, still has a lot to offer. The accumulated experience is a wealth that is only obtained with time.

Ageism and Exclusion: Shadows of the Third Age

Why is the importance of older people no longer valued so much in today's society? Old age has been approached from different perspectives throughout history. However, for several decades the perception that modern societies have of the elderly has remained quite stagnant.

The increase in life expectancy has meant that the main countries of the planet have an increasingly aging population. This not only downplays the importance of having a birthday, but also highlights the emergence of new needs regarding the care and attention that the elderly deserve.

But, is the current society able to adequately assist the elderly population? The problem is twofold: on the one hand, the inability of public administrations to offer an efficient response to these needs and, on the other hand, the inability of many families to successfully face the challenge of caring for an elderly person.

In these circumstances, the simplest solution has been institutionalization in residences. But this alternative does not solve other problems such as distancing or exclusion from social life, lack of participation in important life decisions, age discrimination (ageism) and the consolidation of stereotypes that make older people a 'burden' for society.

In countries such as Australia, Japan or China, where age is still synonymous with wisdom, the contribution of the elderly to cultural, intellectual and political development is valued with special interest. It is these types of attitudes and not those that contribute to distancing, prejudice and loneliness, which should set the course for a change of perspective in favor of recovering the role of older people in society.